

AWARD
Scaling autonomous logistics

D9.2 Plan for the dissemination of the results

—
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List of acronyms

ADS	Autonomous Driving System
ATS	Autonomous Transportation System
C&D	Communication and Dissemination
DoA	Description of Action
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
H2020	Horizon 2020
HDV	Heavy-Duty Vehicles
KPI	Key performance Indicator
M	Month
MS	Milestone
ODD	Operational Design Domain
R&D	Research and Development
SEO	Search Engine Optimisation
T	Task
WP	Work Package
WS	Workshop

1. Executive Summary

Within WP9 “Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation”, this deliverable D9.2 “Plan for the dissemination of the results” reports on the first activities performed under T9.1 “Dissemination and communication activities”.

More specifically, this deliverable outlines the dissemination plan to follow throughout the project, including the project objectives, channels and timeline to successfully and timely disseminate knowledge and results among the relevant stakeholder groups. It also creates and shares physical and digital C&D materials and reaches out to other relevant R&D projects and EC initiatives.

All partners will seek opportunities to communicate and disseminate results through both AWARD channels and their own. Under the coordination of the WP9 leader, the whole consortium will be actively involved in C&D activities to emphasize the importance of the work, and to facilitate effective communication with all the target groups of stakeholders.

This deliverable is coupled with D9.1 “Project website and social network account”¹ that focuses on the AWARD online presence through some already active online channels. The performance of the communication and dissemination (C&D) activities described in this deliverable will be measured through a set of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), whose achievement will be reported in D9.4 “Conferences and education and training report” and D9.5 “Final dissemination report”, both in M36 (December 2023).

¹ AWARD (2021), D9.1 “Project website and social network account”. Available online at: <https://award-h2020.eu/index.php/public-deliverables/>

2. Introduction

2.1. Framework of D9.2

Similarly to D9.1 “Project website and social network account”², this deliverable D9.2 “Plan for the dissemination of the results” is the first measurable result of WP9 “Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation”. This work package acts as the main interface between the project and the outside world. The main objective is to match the project results with exploitation opportunities. Towards this goal, WP9 aims at making the project’s results widely known, establishing links with related on-going research initiatives, explore and assess emerging application areas, and set the foundations for further potential commercial exploitation and opportunities with the identified stakeholders.

D9.2 is part of T9.1 “Dissemination and communication activities”, that will develop and implement an appropriate dissemination and networking strategy and materials. More specifically, it deals with:

- The development of a C&D strategy and plan

The Communication and Dissemination strategy and plan to provide a schedule of tasks and activities for the duration of the project and beyond. This C&D plan will:

- include a clear C&D policy that identifies the relevant audiences to target and the appropriate channels/key stakeholders to use,
- determine how resources will be involved in order to reach an optimal C&D level,
- plan internal events and participation in external ones to maximize the impact,
- identify KPIs to evaluate dissemination strategies and achievements.

- The creation of physical and digital materials

A core set of well-developed online and offline efforts will be carried out to amplify project visibility, including the project visual identity, a website, AWARD profiles on several social network accounts, printable materials, etc. for the convenience of all project partners involved in C&D activities.

- Public awareness, outreach and networking

AWARD will join forces with other similar R&D projects and establish synergies with relevant external bodies and platforms. This networking will materialize with organisation of and participation in joint activities, ranging from physical and virtual events to joint publications, to synchronisation with C&D activities promoted by the EC.

2.2. Dissemination level of D9.2

As a public deliverable of AWARD, D9.2 will be uploaded into the dedicated project webpage (<https://award-h2020.eu/index.php/public-deliverables/>) to allow interested visitors to freely download and further share the project C&D material through their channels. Furthermore, this

² AWARD (2021), D9.1 “Project website and social network account”. Available online at: <https://award-h2020.eu/index.php/public-deliverables/>

will allow other relevant R&D projects and EC initiatives to find synergies with AWARD objectives and planned results, thus facilitating the organisation of joint C&D activities.

2.3. Structure of D9.2

After an executive summary in Section 1, Section 2 places D9.2 in the framework of the DoA³ (WP9 and T9.1). Consequently, the AWARD ambitions and methodology in Section 3 will determine the identification of the most relevant audience (Section 4) and the most appropriate channels to reach them (Section 5). Finally, the deliverable will detail a schedule of C&D activities (Section 6) and a set of KPIs to measure their performance (Section 7) in order to ensure their timely and efficient implementation. Section 8 concludes the document and sheds some lights into the future C&D activities in AWARD.

³ AWARD (2021), Grant Agreement.

3. AWARD excellence

3.1. AWARD ambitions

AWARD (All Weather Autonomous Real logistics operations and Demonstrations) is paving the way for the roll-out of driverless transportation, whatever the weather conditions are. It will deploy safe and efficient connected and automated heavy-duty vehicles in real-life logistics operations. AWARD will bring disruptive changes in the logistic industry by scaling an Autonomous Driving System technology and Fleet Management System for Heavy-Duty Vehicles, within the right safety and functional level to address 24/7 availability.

According to the Grant Agreement⁴, the first ambition of the project is the development of an Autonomous Driving System (ADS) architecture offering a unique set of sensors that enables 24/7 availability (night and day, good or bad weather conditions), within extended Operational Design Domains (ODDs). Secondly, the ADS will be integrated into multiple Heavy-Duty Vehicles (HDV) to be deployed over key pilot projects that are highly scalable and replicable over warehouses, logistics hubs, airports and ports, in mixed traffic in confined areas and on public roads. Finally, logistics operations will be optimized thanks to a new fleet management system. It will integrate data from vehicles, logistics systems and the road infrastructure, coordinating exchanges with different data providers to ensure economic viability of data-related business models, while providing high-reliable and secured tool to optimize logistics flows and ensure safety for other road users. This work will also enable policy recommendations for certifications and approval processes.

3.2. A European vision

AWARD will contribute to the European vision of efficient and safe connected and automated heavy-duty vehicles in real logistics operations⁵. First of all, AWARD contributes to accelerating the deployment of innovative connected and automated freight transport solutions in Europe. Secondly, AWARD increases the overall safety and efficiency of freight operations of individual trucks or fleets through innovative connected and automated driving systems. Thirdly, AWARD supports the uptake of new business models to introduce the automation of logistics operations, while reducing their costs. This will strengthen the European competitiveness in transport and logistics industries. Finally, the evaluation of the AWARD use cases and a deep analysis of the current regulatory framework will feed some policy recommendations to replicate the pilots in other logistics operations.

⁴ AWARD (2021), Grant Agreement.

⁵ European Commission (2019), “DT-ART-05-2020 Efficient and safe connected and automated heavy-duty vehicles in real logistics operations”. Available online at: https://cordis.europa.eu/programme/id/H2020_DT-ART-05-2020

3.3. C&D objectives

According to the AIDA (Awareness – Interest – Decision – Action) methodology⁶, the AWARD communication and dissemination plan aims at:

- Creating awareness of the project objectives and planned results,
- Arousing interest in the project positive impact on the autonomous logistics ecosystem,
- Increasing the credibility and social acceptance of the AWARD results,
- Calling relevant stakeholders to further actions (learning more, getting in contact, participating to surveys and events, engaging in joint activities, adopting the AWARD solutions, etc.)

In addition to promoting the project itself, C&D activities will also convey the wider societal implications of AWARD and their relevance to citizens. In particular, they will align with communication and dissemination initiatives promoted by the EC and other similar R&D projects striving for safer and more efficient connected and automated HDVs in real logistics operations. This will positively influence the acceptance and promote the establishment of a sustainable and acceptable deployment of joint results towards the same European vision.

⁶ R. Priyanka (2013) "AIDA Marketing Communication Model: Stimulating a Purchase Decision in the Minds of the Consumers through a Linear Progression of Steps," in *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research in Social Management*, Vol. 1, pp 37-44.

4. Relevant stakeholder groups

The C&D activities are designed to share and transfer the knowledge and results emerging from AWARD. The aim is to enable selected target audiences to use and take up the project's results from strategic and economic perspective. The consortium members are willing and hoping to obtain useful feedback from the targeted audiences that may take an interest in the use of the results.

Some general principles lead the networking effort, namely:

- Conveying the overall mission of the ATS ecosystem,
- Helping the contributors of the new business value chains in their growth strategy and efforts,
- Capitalizing upon AWARD's best practices and success stories to create a dense network of disruptive and dynamic stakeholders for adopting AWARD technologies and applications,
- Identifying complementarities with local, regional, national and international driverless and logistics related initiatives and programmes for maximum leverage.

However, specific C&D objectives are related to different stakeholder groups, as detailed in Table 1 below, taking into account the classification proposed by the C-ITS Platform⁷.

Table 1: AWARD stakeholder groups and related C&D objectives

Stakeholder group	Description	C&D objectives
Industries and business supporting organisations	Automated freight industry and logistics stakeholders (OEMs, logisticians, freight forwarders, carriers, shipping companies, actors of the local supply chain, etc.), technology providers (software, app, and system developers, platform and cloud computing providers, hardware and service providers, telecom, navigation and map providers), ports, airports, warehouses, logistics hubs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development and marketing of new products, processes, services; • Business development of the AWARD solutions after the project conclusion; • Innovation scouting and investment for more automated freight management ; • Standardisation activities.
Policy makers	Authorities at local, national and international level (members of city councils, city technical services, planning services, regulatory departments, economic development departments, etc.), road operators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implementation of new ATS-related policies and regulatory framework; • Certification of driverless freight vehicles; • Standardisation activities.

⁷ C-ITS Platform (2016), "C-ITS Final report". Available online at: <https://ec.europa.eu/transport/sites/transport/files/themes/its/doc/c-its-platform-final-report-january-2016.pdf>

	(traffic planners, infrastructure owners, maintainers), port authorities, airport authorities	
Research community and academic institutions	Researchers and engineers specialized in automated vehicle technologies, fleet management systems, logistics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transferring and adopting results; • Designing new collaborative research proposals; • Stimulating new research collaboration; • Further research beyond that covered by the project; • Student training; • Education for the academic partners.
Civil society	General public and sectorial press	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communicate AWARD ambitions and results • Communicate the role of the EC and its R&D programs • increase public acceptance of ATS solutions.

5. C&D Channels

The objective of the C&D activities is to reach out to society and show the impact and benefits of AWARD. They will prepare, as broadly as possible, the concerned communities identified in Section 4 to assess, accept, adopt and facilitate turning the AWARD knowledge into a socio-economic viable and sustainable innovation.

Depending on the targets and desired results, the communication channels listed in this section will take into account different strategies to inform about and promote the project and its results and success.

5.1. Physical and digital materials

5.1.1. Logo

The AWARD logo in Figure 1 establishes the project as a brand. Its shape suggests the “A” of AWARD, while the different colours represent the different weather conditions in which the real-life logistics operations will be performed. Additionally, the subtitle “Scaling autonomous logistics”, which was selected by all partners through an open poll, summarises the mission of the project.

Figure 1: AWARD logo

The logo is present in all AWARD C&D materials, thus ensuring coherence of font, colours, etc. throughout the C&D channels.

5.1.2. Flyer

The AWARD first flyer in Figure 2 features the project key messages, real-life logistics operations and expected key results. It also calls the reader to visit the website and follow on social media.

The flyer was created for the convenience of AWARD partners engaging in C&D activities, especially physical events where they will meet interested stakeholders to distribute the flyer to. An updated version of the flyer might be produced in the future, should the necessity arise.

All Weather Autonomous Real logistics operations and Demonstrations

Warehouse
Autonomous loading and unloading forklift operations

Hub-to-hub
Autonomous logistics shuttle service on public road

Airport
Autonomous ground support equipment

Port
Automated transfer operations and ship loading

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 AWARD-H2020
 www.award-h2020.eu

Our key results

Definition of end-user's specifications and requirements

Safe and scalable ADS validated for harsh weather conditions

Zero-Emission Driverless HDVs certified for extended ODDs

Interoperable fleet management and supervision system that optimizes logistics

Demonstrations of automated HDV performing 24/7 real logistics operations

Policy recommendations regarding the regulatory framework

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101006817.

Figure 2: AWARD flyer

5.1.3. Roll up and posters

The AWARD first roll-up in Figure 3 gives key facts about the project, including real-life logistics operations, expected key results and partners involved. It also calls the reader to visit the website and follow on social media.

The flyer was created for the convenience of AWARD partners engaging in C&D activities, especially physical events where they might need to showcase the roll-up. An updated version of the roll-up, as well as several *ad hoc* posters to participate in poster sessions, will be produced in the future, should the necessity arise and upon request of the partners.

Figure 3: AWARD roll-up

5.1.4. Press releases

Press releases will specifically target sectorial press and media professionals. They will be released periodically, especially to promote the project events and achieved results. Figure 4 below shows a thumbnail of the first press release that was distributed after the AWARD Kick-off meeting.

Figure 4: AWARD first press release

All partners are expected to contribute to the dissemination of the AWARD press releases through the diffusion to local and national press in their respective countries.

5.1.5. Newsletter

AWARD is planning on distributing newsletters to the automated transport system community every 6 months to keep interested stakeholders updated about the project developments, results and further ways to get involved.

Table 2: AWARD scheduled newsletters

Number	Date
Newsletter 1	June 2021
Newsletter 2	December 2021

Newsletter 3	June 2022
Newsletter 4	December 2022
Newsletter 5	June 2023
Newsletter 6	December 2023

Visitors of the AWARD website can subscribe to the mailing list, which will be the main distribution channel of the newsletter. In addition, all newsletters will be stored online on the project website and accessible to a large public audience.

All partners are encouraged to invite their connections to subscribe and to further spread the newsletter once they are released.

5.2. Online presence

5.2.1. Website

General public awareness about the project activities will be increased with the AWARD public website (<https://award-h2020.eu/>) which will be monitored through detailed analytics. All communication documents will be made available (digital material, public deliverables, presentations, newsletters, publications, etc.) The AWARD website will be maintained 3 years after the project conclusion for supporting the project impacts.

The number of website visits will increase thanks to different expedients. First of all, the AWARD website is graphically pleasant, conceptually clear, user-friendly and responsive. Secondly, the website content is optimized for search engines through image alt texts, featured images, meta descriptions, keywords, internal links, etc. Thirdly, the website content will be promoted through social media and newsletters, that will include links to dedicated pages and posts on the AWARD website. Also, a direct link to the web is included in the AWARD signature (cf. Figure 5). Finally, AWARD partners and a number of multipliers (projects, ecosystems, networks, initiatives) will be encouraged to promote AWARD through their C&D channels, thus increasing the chances of receiving inbound links to the project website (cf. section 5.2.3).

An extended description of the AWARD website is available in D9.2 “Project website and social network account”⁸.

5.2.2. Social networks

Different social network profiles have been activated to maximize the visibility of AWARD results and of the partners engaging in the project activities:

- <https://www.linkedin.com/company/award-h2020/>
- https://twitter.com/award_h2020
- <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCOUPqUdn7JlbUYu7MexdzfQ>

⁸ AWARD (2021), D9.1 “Project website and social network account”. Available online at: <https://award-h2020.eu/index.php/public-deliverables/>

The project social media networks will be populated with images, pictures, infographics, videos and other audio-visual media showing the project demonstrations and results as soon as they are available.

The feedback received on social media (e.g., number and type of followers, comments regarding the project activities, etc.) will be carefully analysed and managed to further enhance the project online presence. The WP9 leader commits to monitor the activity on social media every day, to comply with the 24h response time envisaged by the associated KPI ([cf. Section 7](#)).

On the other hand, most KPIs measure the performance of the AWARD social networks through the number of publications and the number of followers ([cf. Section 7](#)), as their main goal is to increase the visibility of the project. In order to reach a far audience of followers, AWARD will post consistently on its social networks, coupling its posts with specific hashtags, such as #IntelligentTransportSystem, #SustainableLogistics, #SupplyChainManagement, #OperationalResearch, #Truck, #Automation, #CAV, #LogisticsOperations, #AutonomousTransportSystem, #ATS, #FleetmanagementSystem, #Demonstration, #PilotProject, #AutonomousDrivingSystem, #ADS. In addition, posts will mention other similar projects, EU initiatives and platforms, and influencers in the ATS sector. Especially on Twitter, a well-crafted list of following accounts will increase the possibilities of being followed back by those accounts. Finally, all AWARD partners will reach out to their connections through their social media channels and invite them to follow the project.

An extended description of the AWARD social media profiles is available in D9.1 “Project website and social network account”⁹.

5.2.3. Visual identity

AWARD will be integrated into the landscape of advanced research, development, and demonstration programs that are closely linked to the field of autonomous transport systems. Hence, the project will join forces with several similar initiatives that are presented on a dedicated webpage online (<https://award-h2020.eu/index.php/collaborations/>).

On the other hand, AWARD needs to be visible and widely known in the panorama of ATS. Therefore, AWARD has already been included into the CAD Knowledge Base: <https://knowledge-base.connectedautomateddriving.eu/>. A number of multipliers (projects, ecosystems, networks, initiatives) will be encouraged to promote AWARD through their C&D channels.

In addition, each consortium member will have a dedicated section to the project in their own organisation website.

Finally, all AWARD members involved in the project activities are encouraged to sign their email correspondence with the dedicated AWARD signature:

⁹ AWARD (2021), D9.1 “Project website and social network account”. Available online at: <https://award-h2020.eu/index.php/public-deliverables/>

Name Surname

Job Title

[WEBSITE](#) | [LINKEDIN](#) | [TWITTER](#) | [YOUTUBE](#)

Figure 5: AWARD signature

5.3. Publications and open access

The AWARD partners commit to make the project public results (i.e., non-confidential) available online for any user. This commitment specifically applies to public deliverables and scientific papers.

5.3.1. Public deliverables

Throughout the project lifetime, a number of public deliverables will be produced as a result of the AWARD activities. They will be stored on a dedicated webpage online (<https://award-h2020.eu/index.php/public-deliverables/>).

A preliminary list of platforms where AWARD will be sharing its public deliverables is as follows:

- The AWARD website
- ZENODO¹⁰, a joint CERN and OpenAIRE open-source repository of academic publications and data
- ALICE Knowledge platform¹¹
- CAD Knowledge Base¹²

Table 3 below lists the AWARD public deliverables, their authors and expected submission date.

Table 3: AWARD public deliverables

No.	Title	Related Task	Lead	Type	Due Date
D2.1	System Scope	T2.1	EASYMILE	Report	M9 Sep 2021
D2.2	User and Stakeholder Requirements	T2.2	AIT	Report	M9 Sep 2021
D3.5	Public architecture design report	T3.1	EASYMILE	Report	M12 Dec 2021
D3.6	Public report for measurement campaigns of ADS	T3.3	EASYMILE	Report	M16

¹⁰ ZENODO, <https://zenodo.org/>

¹¹ ALICE Knowledge platform, <https://knowledgeplatform.etp-logistics.eu/>

¹² CAD Knowledge base, <https://knowledge-base.connectedautomateddriving.eu/>

					Apr 2022
D4.4	Factory Acceptance test report	T4.2	EASYMILE	Report	M15 Mar 2021
D4.6	Public safety Documents including Safety plan, Hazard Analysis and Risk Assessment, Functional and technical safety concepts	T4.1	EASYMILE	Report	M11 Nov 2021
D4.7	Safety Evaluation report: Assessment report	T4.3	CertX AG	Report	M24 Dec 2022
D5.7	Public Architectural model for fleet management and control services	T5.1	Applied Auto	Demonstrator	M8 Aug 2021
D7.1	Test and evaluation plan	T7.1	VTT	Report	M12 Dec 2021
D7.3	Impact assessment and user survey results	T7.3 / T7.4	ENIDE	Report	M36 Dec 2023
D7.4	Final test and evaluation plan	T7.1	VTT	Report	M24 Dec 2022
D8.1	Market opportunities, barriers and solutions	T8.1	ENIDE	Report	M12 Dec 2021
D8.4	Recommendations - regulatory and governance frameworks	T8.4	CertX AG	Report	M36 Dec 2023
D8.5	Final market opportunities, barriers and solutions	T8.1	ENIDE	Report	M34 Oct 2022
D9.1	Project website and social network account	T9.1	ENIDE	Websites, patents filling, etc.	M3 Mar 2021
D9.2	Plans for dissemination of the results	T9.1	ENIDE	Report	M3 Mar 2021
D9.4	Conferences and Education and training report	T9.3	CARA	Report	M36 Dec 2023
D9.5	Final dissemination report	T9.1	ENIDE	Report	M36 Dec 2023
D9.7	Roadmap towards connected and automated heavy-duty vehicles for logistics operations	T9.4	ENIDE	Report	M36 Dec 2023
D10.1	Project handbook	T10.2	EASYMILE	Report	M3 Mar 2021
D10.2	Impact assessment methodology	T10.3	ENIDE	Report	M12 Dec 2021
D10.5	Data Management Plan	T10.2	EASYMILE	ORDP	M6 Jun 2021

5.3.2. Scientific papers

Throughout the project lifetime, the AWARD partners envision a number of scientific papers (cf. Section 7) to be submitted to renowned conferences (cf. Section 5.3.2) and journals in the field of ATS. A preliminary list of target international scientific journals is as follows:

- Atmospheric research
- IEEE Intelligent Transportation System Magazine
- IEEE Intelligent Transportation Systems Transactions
- IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation
- IEEE Transactions on Microwave Theory and Techniques
- IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks and Learning Systems
- IEEE Sensors Journal
- International Journal of Automotive Technology
- MPDI Journal of Applied Science
- Springer Journal of Machine Vision and Applications
- Personal and Ubiquitous Computing Journal
- Transportation Research Part F

Complying with Article 29.2 of Grant Agreement¹³, “each beneficiary must ensure open access (free of charge online access for any user) to all peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to its results.”

The principle of open access will be achieved by targeting publishers that provide ‘gold’ open access, either by making the articles immediately available online free of charge, or by having each affiliated partner to cover the relevant cost. Whenever the ‘gold’ open access model cannot be applicable, we will take the benefits of the ‘green’ model instead, by supplementary publishing the relevant articles to an online repository, in consultation with the publisher, in case that an embargo period is needed. Furthermore, many publishers also allow the publication for educational purposes of the accepted manuscript, if the version of the paper before the final editing and formulation made by the editing office is used.

Figure 6 below summarises the two options to grant open access to scientific publications, according to Article 29.2 of Grant Agreement¹⁴.

¹³ AWARD (2021), Grant Agreement.

¹⁴ AWARD (2021), Grant Agreement.

Figure 6: Open Access summary

A preliminary list of platforms where AWARD will be sharing scientific papers is as follows:

- The AWARD website
- ZENODO¹⁵, a joint CERN and OpenAIRE open-source repository of academic publications and data
- ALICE Knowledge platform¹⁶
- CAD Knowledge Base¹⁷

The AWARD partners strongly believe that by giving open access to our scientific publications will aim to speed up important breakthroughs by the European researchers that will lead to boost knowledge and competitiveness in Europe.

5.4. Events

5.4.1. Organisation of internal events

5.4.1.1. Workshops

As part of the stakeholder engagement activities, WP9 is planning several workshops to support different project goals: stakeholders' requirements collection and analysis, evaluation, identification of emerging business models, development of regulatory and governance frameworks, etc. Co-creation approaches will offer social dynamic face-to-face interactions which will add enormous value to the consultation processes.

¹⁵ ZENODO, <https://zenodo.org/>

¹⁶ ALICE Knowledge platform, <https://knowledgeplatform.etp-logistics.eu/>

¹⁷ CAD Knowledge base, <https://knowledge-base.connectedautomateddriving.eu/>

Six workshops will be organized together with WP2, WP7 and WP8. Each workshop will be organized by one of the five network partners: IRU, BizUp, CARA, CEREMA and ITS Norway. Table 4 below provides a tentative schedule of WSs during the project lifetime:

Table 4: AWARD scheduled workshops

Number	Date
Workshop 1	2021
Workshop 2	2021
Workshop 3	2022
Workshop 4	2022
Workshop 5	2023
Workshop 6	2023

5.4.1.2. Visits to demonstration sites

WP6 “Autonomous driving demonstrations in real logistics operations” will be responsible of deploying four ATs to tackle technological challenges related to autonomous logistics operations in mixed traffic in port, airport and warehouses. The different pilot project sites will host potential customers throughout the demonstrations duration, starting from M27 (March 2023).

The specific KPI dedicated to the customer visits to the AWARD pilot sites is available in [Section 7](#).

5.4.1.3. Stakeholder conferences

Two conferences will be organized to present and discuss the project with the scientific community as well as with transport and logistic operators. To ensure a large audience, the consortium will present the project at two existing events: SOLUTRANS 2023 & VREF Conference (Volvo Research and Education Foundations) 2023 which gather a large and international academic community. CARA will coordinate the organisation of AWARD’s conferences in both events, with a target of 150 registered participants.

5.4.1.4. Education and training

An education and training program will be organised to share knowledge of technologies related to autonomous HDVs in order to train students, workers and researchers. For these courses, the consortium will provide access to project’s test sites, pilot and demonstration facilities. These activities will be supported and disseminated by R&D and academic partners. To ensure quality education and training and dissemination, this task will rely on the existing Automotive & Electromobility Campus and related pilot line of CARA in France as well as on its network of partners. Pilots’ coordinators (WP6) will allow the access to the demonstration site and will give support as experts in the education and training program. CARA will build on the resources and expertise from the Automotive & Electromobility Campus to coordinate the education & training program and ensure dissemination.

5.4.2. Participation in external events

Participation to international events and synergies with other projects will be sought as much as possible in order to increase readiness awareness of the AWARD technologies and get feedback from experts in the community that may help eventually to build a consolidated and complementary vision for the EU industrial value chain.

Other bodies will also be targeted, via events organised by the International Road Transport Union, for example the IRU EU Conference, IRU World Congress, IRU Logistics and Innovation Forum or ITS Europe/ITS World. In addition, CARA will also mobilize its members to collect their inputs and disseminate the project. Finally, some of these events welcome the submission of scientific papers, thus helping achieve the KPI of publications (cf. Section 7).

A preliminary list of targeted events is as follows:

- A3PS Conference - Vienna 2021 and following years
- ACM Automotive'UI 2021, 2022, 2023
- Autonomous Machines World 2022, 2023
- Automotive, yearly congress organised by BIZUP/ Automotive-Cluster in Upper Austria
- EUCAD annual conferences
- IAA Commercial Vehicles 2021, Munich
- IEEE Intelligent Vehicles Symposium 2022, 2023
- IEEE International Intelligent transport System Conference 2022, 2023
- International Vienna Motor Symposium
- IPIC annual conferences
- ITS World 2021, Hamburg & ITS Europe 2021, 2022, 2023
- IRU World Congress 2022 (location to be announced)
- SIL BARCELONA Expo & Congress
- SOLUTRANS 2023
- TRA 2022
- VREF Conference
- Zukunftsforum OÖ, yearly congress co-organised by BIZUP/ Automotive-Cluster in Upper Austria

6. C&D activities schedule

The stage of project activities decisively influences the kind and content of C&D efforts. During the first preparation phase, the main objective is to raise awareness about the project and building up a network of cooperating stakeholders to get the necessary feedback to inform the scientific and technical developments. Later on, during the project lifetime, demonstrations of real-life automated logistics operations will produce sound project findings that will allow for presentations and publications among the stakeholders' groups identifies in the early stages of AWARD.

C&D activities will intensify in connection with the achievement of the project milestones. Table 5 below lists the project milestones, their due date and responsible WP.

Table 5: AWARD milestones

No	Due date	Milestone name	Related WP
MS1	M9 – 30th September 2021	System scope and requirements specified	WP2
MS2	M12 – 31st December 2021	Architecture design	WP3
MS3	M16 – 30th April 2022	ADS ready for integration into HDV	WP3
MS4	M13 – 31st January 2022	Safety and technical HDV specifications	WP4
MS5	M17 – 31st May 2022	Factory Acceptance Tests	WP4
MS6	M22 – 31st October 2022	Fleet management system and HMI ready for pilots	WP5
MS7	M36 – 31st December 2023	Cybersecurity penetration test	WP5
MS8	M27 – 31st March 2023	Demonstration launch	WP6
MS9	M24 – 31st December 2022	Test and evaluation plan ready	WP7
MS10	M36 – 31st December 2023	Regulatory and governance frameworks recommendations	WP8

Table 6 below shows the allocation of time and resources during the three years lifetime of AWARD. C&D activities will adapt channels and input to the target audience in order to reach a specific C&D objective.

Table 6: AWARD stakeholder groups and related C&D objectives

Input	Stakeholder groups	C&D channels	C&D objectives
C&D objective in year 1: Create awareness			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presentation of AWARD ambitions and 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Industries and business 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Physical and digital materials • Online presence 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wide visibility

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> expected results • Presentation of MSs 1,2 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> supporting organisations • Research community and academic institutions • General public 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participation in external events • Organisation of WS 1, 2 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Attract interested stakeholders • Get constructive feedback for further technical developments
C&D objective in year 2: Evaluation and economic viability			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presentation of AWARD use-cases • Presentation of MSs 3,4,5,6,9 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Industries and business supporting organisations • Policy makers • Scientific and academic institutions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Physical and digital materials • Online presence • Participation in external events • Scientific publications • Organisation of WSs 3, 4 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evaluate the project first findings • Improve the project positioning among relevant stakeholders • Inform EC authorities
C&D objective in year 3: Sustainability and replicability of results			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Demonstration of AWARD solutions • Presentation of MSs 7,8,10 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Industries and business supporting organisations • Policy makers • Scientific and academic institutions • Press and general public 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Physical and digital materials • Online presence • Scientific publications • Organisation of WSs 5, 6 • Special sessions in major sectorial events (SOLUTRANS, VREF Conference) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Find opportunities for further research, funding and exploitation • Inform the EC authorities

Since T9.1 is also responsible for monitoring the participation of partners in relevant events, C&D activities report has been created and shared on the project online repository, which is accessible only to AWARD partners.

On the one hand, this living document will support the AWARD partners in reporting their efforts in C&D activities to the EC, on the other hand it will help them plan the potential future activities to maximize the visibility of the project.

7. Key Performance Indicators

AWARD has set ambitious C&D objectives, whose performance will be monitored through the list of KPIs available in Table 7 below.

Table 7: AWARD C&D KPIs

C&D channel		KPI	Value by M36
Online presence	Website	Number of single visits	>3000
	Social networks	1000 new followers per year	3000 followers
		Number of tweets	>2000
		Number of posts on LinkedIn	>300
		Response time on social media	>24 hours
Visual identity	Number of multipliers (projects, ecosystems, networks, initiatives) engaged to promote AWARD	>15	
Publications	Conference papers	Number of publications	30
	Journals papers	Number of publications	10
Events	Workshops	Number of workshops	6
	Visits to demonstrations sites of the different pilot project sites	Number of potential customers invited to pilot project sites	150
	AWARD conferences in SOLUTRANS and VREF	Number of registered participants	150
	Complementary events in which AWARD is promoted	Number of events	>10

During the project lifetime, the consortium meetings described in D10.6 “Project management plan”¹⁸ will be the occasion to report on the performance of C&D activities. In M36, D9.4 “Conferences and education and training report” and D9.5 “Final dissemination report” will report the achievement of the KPIs identified in D9.2.

¹⁸ AWARD (2021), D10.6 “Project management plan”.

8. Conclusion

AWARD envisioned WP9 “Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation” to make the project visible and widely known and to establish links with relevant stakeholders. This deliverable D9.2 “Plan for the dissemination of the results” focuses on the definition of a dissemination strategy to support all partners in their C&D efforts.

This deliverable defined the dissemination plan, detailing the project ambitions, target stakeholders and appropriate channels to reach them, useful and coherent C&D materials, as well as the networking commitment with other EC initiatives and R&D projects.

Under the guidance of the WP9 leader, all partners will proactively look for opportunities and actively engage activities to communicate and disseminate AWARD. Therefore, the continuous monitoring of the partners’ C&D efforts will make D9.2 a living document that will develop in parallel with the achievement of AWARD milestones.

This deliverable is coupled with D9.1 “Project website and social network account”¹⁹ that delves into the AWARD online presence. During the project lifetime, the consortium meetings will be the occasion to report on the performance of C&D activities compared to the set of KPIs listed in this deliverable. Finally, at the end of the project (M36, December 2023), D9.4 “Conferences and education and training report” and D9.5 “Final dissemination report” will report the achievement of the KPIs identified in D9.2.

¹⁹ AWARD (2021), D9.1 “Project website and social network account”. Available online at: <https://award-h2020.eu/index.php/public-deliverables/>

Annex 1: Obligation to disseminate results

Article 29.1 of the Grant Agreement²⁰ states:

“Unless it goes against their legitimate interests, each beneficiary must - as soon as possible - ‘disseminate’ its results by disclosing them to the public by appropriate means (other than those resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including in scientific publications (in any medium).

This does not change the obligation to protect results in Article 27, the confidentiality obligations in Article 36, the security obligations in Article 37 or the obligations to protect personal data in Article 39, all of which still apply.

A beneficiary that intends to disseminate its results must give advance notice to the other beneficiaries of — unless agreed otherwise — at least 45 days, together with sufficient information on the results it will disseminate.

Any other beneficiary may object within — unless agreed otherwise — 30 days of receiving notification, if it can show that its legitimate interests in relation to the results or background would be significantly harmed. In such cases, the dissemination may not take place unless appropriate steps are taken to safeguard these legitimate interests.

If a beneficiary intends not to protect its results, it may — under certain conditions (see Article 26.4.1) — need to formally notify the Agency before dissemination takes place.”

²⁰ AWARD (2021), Grant Agreement.

Annex 2: Template for dissemination notice

This annex provides a template message from a beneficiary that intends to disseminate its results to the other beneficiaries, based on the guidelines included in the Grant Agreement²¹ and in the Consortium Agreement²².

Dear all,

In coordination with WP9 and WP10, the partners xxx have prepared the article entitled “XXX” (Link here) to be submitted to the “XXX” event.

Complying with Article 29.1 of the AWARD Grant Agreement, we are giving prior notice of this planned publication 45 calendar days before its occurrence. Furthermore, complying with Article 10 of the Consortium Agreement, we declare that the publication is not disclosing confidential information.

In case any legitimate interest in relation to the results or background could be significantly harmed, objections must be raised within 30 calendar days from the notice, by writing to the Project Coordinator and the beneficiaries involved in the publication. If no objection is made within the time limit stated above, the publication is allowed.

Therefore, we kindly ask you to review the article and to communicate any objection until <DATE> EOB.

²¹ AWARD (2021), Grant Agreement.

²² AWARD (2021), Consortium Agreement.

Annex 3: H2020 Dissemination guidelines

Article 29 of the Grant Agreement²³ states:

“Unless the Agency requests or agrees otherwise or unless it is impossible, any dissemination of results (in any form, including electronic) must:

- (a) display the EU emblem and
- (b) include the following text:

“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101006817”.

When displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem must have appropriate prominence.

For the purposes of their obligations under this Article, the beneficiaries may use the EU emblem without first obtaining approval from the Agency.

This does not however give them the right to exclusive use.

Moreover, they may not appropriate the EU emblem or any similar trademark or logo, either by registration or by any other means.

Any dissemination of results must indicate that it reflects only the author's view and that the Agency is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.”

²³ AWARD (2021), Grant Agreement.

Annex 4: Template for presentations

A template for PowerPoint presentation is available for AWARD partners on the online repository. Figure 7 below provides a thumbnail.

Figure 7: AWARD presentation template

References

- [1] AWARD (2021), D9.1 “project website and social network account”. Available online at: <https://award-h2020.eu/index.php/public-deliverables/>
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- [13] AWARD (2021), Grant Agreement.
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- [20] AWARD (2021), Grant Agreement.
- [21] AWARD (2021), Grant Agreement.
- [22] AWARD (2021), Consortium Agreement.
- [23] AWARD (2021), Grant Agreement.